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Theoretical aspects of management of organizational transformations in the process of enterprise development in modern conditions

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the study of the process of managing an enterprise's organizational transformations in modern conditions. The purpose of this work is to study the process of management of organizational transformations of enterprise in modern conditions. Research has shown that in recent years, businesses have recognized the importance of being prepared for unpredictable changes (for example, the COVID-19 pandemic and hostilities in Ukraine, which have impacted

nearly every industry). Enterprises that were ready for rapid transformations could respond quickly and adapt to new conditions.

It is proved that the management of organizational transformations today is a critically important process for the development of an enterprise. Effective change management allows enterprises to remain competitive and lay the foundation for long-term success. Enterprises that can quickly and qualitatively adapt to new conditions have a higher chance of survival and prosperity in the market. Effective transformation management helps to achieve sustainable development, which is a crucial condition for the success of an enterprise in the long term.

It has been established that the factors stimulating enterprises to change are divided into external ones, which dictate the need to adapt to the market and new regulatory requirements, and internal ones, which indicate the possibilities of increasing efficiency and improving the culture and organization of labor. The need for transformations is generally determined by the enterprise's desire to remain competitive, develop, and meet the new requirements of society and the market.

The main types of organizational changes are identified, which aim to improve the relevant aspects of the enterprise's activities. Each type of transformation meets specific needs and forms a holistic system for the successful development of the enterprise. Understanding different types of transformations helps enterprises choose the appropriate approach to change and adapt to the market.

Effective transformation management is critical for the success of the enterprise. It allows us to respond to current challenges and pave the way for long-term development and sustainable success. Choosing the type of transformation and understanding the factors that stimulate change allows the enterprise to use its resources as efficiently as possible and move forward confidently.

Keywords: business environment, innovation, competitiveness, corporate culture, organizational transformation, enterprise development, transformation management, digitalization.

Теоретичні аспекти управління організаційними трансформаціями в процесі розвитку підприємства у сучасних умовах

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Анотація. Статтю присвячено дослідженню процесу управління організаційними трансформаціями підприємства в сучасних умовах. Метою статті є дослідження процесу управління організаційними трансформаціями підприємства в сучасних умовах. Дослідження показало, що останніми роками бізнеси усвідомили важливість готовності до непередбачуваних змін (прикладом є пандемія COVID-19 та воєнні дії в Україні, які змінили майже всі галузі). Підприємства, готові до швидких трансформацій, могли оперативно реагувати та адаптуватися до нових умов.

Доведено, що управління організаційними трансформаціями сьогодні є критично важливим процесом для розвитку підприємства. Ефективне керування змінами дозволяє підприємствам не лише залишатися конкурентоспроможними, але й закладати фундамент для довгострокового успіху. Підприємства, які здатні швидко та якісно адаптуватися до нових умов, мають вищі шанси на виживання та процвітання на ринку. Ефективне

управління трансформаціями допомагає досягти стійкого розвитку, що є ключовою умовою для успіху підприємства в довгостроковій перспективі.

Встановлено, що фактори, стимулюючі підприємства до змін, поділяються на **зовнішні**, які диктують потребу в адаптації до ринку та нових вимог регуляторів та **внутрішні**, які вказують на можливості підвищення ефективності та покращення культури й організації праці. Загалом, потреба в трансформаціях зумовлена бажанням підприємства залишатися конкурентним, розвиватися й відповідати новим вимогам суспільства та ринку.

Виокремлено основні види організаційних змін, які спрямовані на покращення відповідних аспектів діяльності підприємства. Кожен вид трансформацій відповідає на специфічні потреби і формує цілісну систему для успішного розвитку підприємства. Розуміння різних видів трансформацій допомагає підприємствам обрати відповідний підхід до змін і адаптуватися до ринку.

Наголошено на тому, що ефективне управління трансформаціями є критичним для успіху підприємства. Воно дозволяє не лише реагувати на поточні виклики, але й прокладати шлях до довгострокового розвитку та стійкого успіху. Вибір виду трансформації та розуміння чинників, що стимулюють зміни, дає змогу підприємству максимально ефективно використовувати свої ресурси та впевнено рухатися вперед.

Ключові слова: бізнес-середовище, інновації, конкурентоспроможність, корпоративна культура, організаційні трансформації, розвиток підприємства, управління трансформаціями, цифровізація.

Statement of the problem. The world is becoming increasingly dynamic. Technological innovation, globalization, changes in consumer preferences, and economic fluctuations require businesses to adapt constantly.

Technology is changing the business landscape faster than ever before. New digital solutions, artificial intelligence, automation, and innovation require businesses

to adapt. Those who actively implement digital transformations reach a new level of customer service faster and reduce operating costs. At the same time, introducing new technologies requires the right strategy and transparent change management to avoid chaos and resistance among staff.

In addition, modern consumers are becoming increasingly demanding. Today, they are looking for businesses that offer a personalized approach, environmental friendliness, speed of service, and innovative products. Businesses must restructure their operations and structures to meet market expectations — from marketing to production processes. Transformation management helps businesses understand these changes and respond to them correctly.

Globalization and increased competition are also adjusting this process. With the growth of globalization, Ukrainian enterprises are forced to compete with local and international players, who often have a higher level of technology and access to much more extensive resources. Businesses must adapt their business models to operate successfully in such an environment, often accompanied by organizational changes. In addition, transformations allow enterprises to enter international markets using new approaches and management standards.

Many businesses have realized the importance of being prepared for unpredictable changes in recent years (an example is the COVID-19 pandemic and the hostilities in Ukraine, which have changed almost every industry). Enterprises ready for rapid transformations could react quickly and adapt to new conditions. This shows that in today's business environment, businesses must be able to rebuild quickly, and transformation management is becoming a critical factor in such adaptability.

In today's world, businesses are increasingly faced with the requirements of profitability and responsibility to society and the environment. Requirements for transparency, environmental responsibility, and ethical business conduct are becoming the norm. To meet these expectations, enterprises need organizational

transformations, which include a revision of management approaches, a new corporate culture, and updated business processes.

The modern labor market also requires new approaches to personnel management - from developing staff skills to creating a comfortable working environment. The younger generation of employees values wages, opportunities for development, corporate culture, and an innovative approach to work. Businesses must transform, including modernizing their workforce approaches to attract and retain talent.

Therefore, the above emphasizes the relevance and importance of organizational transformation management in modern conditions, when enterprises face numerous challenges and rapid changes in the market.

Analysis of the latest research and publications. The works of domestic scientists, namely S. H. Ajeel [15], D. Anderson [9], A. Armenakis [16], S.I. Bai [1], L.O. Denysenko [6], S. U. Devi [11], L.Y. Gordienko [2, 3], E.L. Gryn [3], T.V. Grinko [5], T.Z. Gviniashvili [5], S.G. Harris [16], H. Kadim [14], A.H. Kataa [12], R. Kiruba Nagini [11], I. J. Klein [13], R. Magalhaes [10], S. Mohamed [11], K.R. Nemashkalo [7], H.M. O'Neill [13], S.V. Stepanenko [8], and others revealed theoretical and practical aspects of managing organizational transformations of enterprises.

Identification of previously unresolved aspects of the overall problem. Despite the extensive coverage of this topic in the works of leading researchers, universally accepted theoretical foundations for managing organizational transformations in the process of enterprise development are not presented in the scientific literature. Also despite numerous studies on this issue, in conditions of uncertainty (in particular, epidemics and military operations), these issues require further research, analysis, systematization, and improvement.

Formulation of the article's objectives (statement of the task). The purpose of this work is to study the process of management of organizational transformations of enterprise in modern conditions.

Statement of the main material. Organizational transformations are systemic, profound changes aimed at improving the enterprise's performance, adapting to external and internal challenges, and increasing its efficiency and competitiveness [2]. Their essence lies in restructuring existing business processes, structures, and approaches to management so that the enterprise can grow and develop sustainably even in the face of rapid changes.

The factors that encourage enterprises to perform organizational transformations can be generally divided into external and internal (Fig. 1, compiled based on [2, 3, 4]). Each of these groups plays a significant role in determining the need for change and the direction in which to move.

External factors refer to the conditions that surround the enterprise and are usually beyond its control. Let us take a closer look at the main ones:

1. Competition in the market. Increased competition encourages businesses to change their approaches to maintain a competitive advantage. This may include upgrading products, improving customer service, or introducing new technologies.

2. Economic situation. Economic fluctuations, inflation, changes in exchange rates, and other economic factors force businesses to adapt their strategies. For example, enterprises can optimize costs during economic instability or change the production structure.

3. Change in consumer preferences. When consumer tastes and expectations change, businesses must adapt quickly to stay in demand. For example, the trend towards sustainability is forcing them to switch to environmentally friendly materials and processes.

4. Technological progress. Technological innovations open up new opportunities but threaten enterprises that need more time to adapt. Such businesses are often forced to invest in digital transformation to remain competitive.

5. Legislative regulation. Adopting new laws or tightening existing regulations (e.g., environmental, tax, labor) may force businesses to change their operational processes or products to comply with regulations.

6. Globalization. Due to the growth of international relations, businesses are often forced to adapt to new conditions. This may include expanding into new markets, adapting products to international standards, or changing the supply chain.

Figure. 1. Factors driving enterprises to transform

Source: developed by authors

Internal factors reflect the characteristics of the enterprise itself, and the organization has a more significant influence on them, namely:

1. Organizational strategy. If a business updates its mission, vision, or strategic goals, it often requires significant changes in structure or processes. For example, shifting to a customer-centric strategy may require marketing, customer service changes, and more.

2. Development of corporate culture. Changes in corporate values and operating principles (e.g., a focus on innovation or sustainability) also lead to changes in internal processes and structure.

3. Efficiency and productivity. The need to improve performance or product quality can push for transformation. This includes implementing new management systems, quality control processes, and automation.

4. Employee initiatives. Sometimes, the need for change arises from staff initiatives, especially if the company has a strong culture of innovation or involvement in decision-making. Employees may come up with new ideas or improvements that require organizational change.

5. Financial condition of the enterprise. The need for transformation may be driven by a desire to improve your financial situation. For example, if a business has high costs, this may push for reorganization or optimization of business processes.

6. Change of leadership. A leader or top management change often brings a new perspective on development and can drive change. New management usually brings its own management style, values, and strategy vision, which can drastically affect the enterprise.

7. Reaction to previous failures. If a business has faced problems due to inefficient processes or strategies, this can be an incentive for profound change. Learning from previous experiences and adapting to the findings helps to avoid repeating mistakes.

First, it is essential to analyze the external environment regularly for effective transformation management. PESTLE analysis helps assess political, economic, social, technological, legal, and environmental factors (environmental).

In addition, internal factors must be assessed through a SWOT analysis, which examines the enterprise's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats.

An equally important step is to compare external and internal factors with the existing strategy to understand how ready the company is for the necessary changes.

Understanding these factors allows you to be better prepared to manage organizational change, minimize risks, and focus on those aspects that will most significantly impact the success of transformations.

Analysis of scientific papers [1, 4, 6 - 16] allows us to distinguish several types of organizational transformations, each corresponding to the enterprise's specific needs and the scale of changes that need to be made. Let us consider the most common types of organizational transformations, namely:

1. Strategic transformations. This type of transformation aims to change the overall strategy of the enterprise. Usually, strategic transformations involve rethinking the company's business model, new customer approaches, or significant product range changes.

The key features are a change in the mission, vision, business model, or market in which the company operates. For example, a company that previously specialized in producing print publications is moving to online media, adapting its business model to the digital economy.

2. Operational transformations aim to improve the efficiency of the company's internal processes, reduce costs, and increase productivity.

The key features are process optimization, automation, cost reduction, increased productivity, and quality. For example, implementing automated inventory management systems in the warehouse can reduce costs and increase the speed of order processing.

3. Digital transformations (digitalization). Modern enterprises actively implement digital technologies to improve their processes and increase competitiveness. These can be changes in both customer service and operational processes.

The key features are implementing IT solutions such as data analytics, artificial intelligence, automation, etc. For example, a retail chain is creating a mobile app for ease of purchase that allows customers to order products online and receive personalized offers based on the analysis of purchase data.

4. Cultural transformations. Changes in corporate culture may be necessary to implement other types of transformations or to improve the work environment. Cultural change is usually related to the company's values, norms of conduct, ethical principles, and employee motivation.

The key features of such a transformation are changes in values, motivational programs, working approaches, and relations between employees and management. For example, a company that wants to become more innovative changes its corporate culture by encouraging creativity and flexibility in employees' work.

5. Organizational and structural transformations. This type of change involves reorganizing the enterprise's structure, including redistribution of powers, creating new divisions or merger of existing ones, and optimizing the hierarchy. The goal is to increase the organization's efficiency and adaptability to change.

The key features are department reorganization, optimization of management levels, and function redistribution. For example, an enterprise moves from a hierarchical to a matrix structure, allowing for better interaction between departments and faster adaptation to market changes.

6. Innovative transformations. This change introduces innovations to improve products, services, or processes.

Among the key features are introducing new technologies, developing new products, or radical changes in business processes. For example, a manufacturing company implements robotic technology on the production line, allowing for increased production speed and quality.

7. Marketing transformations. Such changes are needed to adapt to new consumer behavior trends or develop new markets. This can include reimagining the brand, changing distribution channels, and taking new customer communication approaches.

Such transformations feature the development of new sales channels, a change in brand strategy, and the introduction of digital marketing tools. For example, a brand

is shifting to influencer marketing to attract a younger audience and expand its influence on social media.

8. Financial transformations. Financial changes often aim to optimize the cost structure and manage the enterprise's profitability and liquidity. These can involve changes in asset management, capital expenditures, or financing.

The key features of financial transformation are optimizing financial flows, debt restructuring, and changes in the accounting and cost management system. For example, a company restructures its debt to reduce interest costs and free up funds for developing new projects.

9. Environmental transformations. Pursuing sustainable development pushes businesses to make environmental changes to reduce their environmental impact. This becomes an essential factor in competitiveness and customer engagement.

Such changes include reducing emissions, introducing resource-saving technologies, and using renewable energy sources. For example, the company is switching to biodegradable packaging and renewable energy sources, demonstrating its commitment to environmental protection.

Implementing transformations can combine several types. For example, cultural or structural changes can accompany digital changes, creating a comprehensive approach to business development.

Conclusion. The study allows us to draw the following conclusions:

1. Today, managing organizational transformations is not just a fashionable trend but a critical process for the development of the enterprise. Effective change management allows businesses to stay competitive and lay the foundation for long-term success. Businesses that can quickly and efficiently adapt to new conditions have a higher chance of surviving and thriving in the market. Effective transformation management helps to achieve sustainable development, which is a crucial condition for the success of the enterprise in the long term.

2. The factors that stimulate enterprises to change are divided into external factors, which dictate the need to adapt to the market and new regulatory

requirements, and internal factors, which indicate the possibility of increasing efficiency and improving the culture and organization of work. The need for transformation is generally due to the company's desire to remain competitive, develop, and meet the new requirements of society and the market.

3. Understanding the different types of transformations helps businesses choose the appropriate approach to change and adapt to the market. Various organizational changes aim to improve the relevant aspects of the enterprise's activities. Strategic transformations allow you to update the overall direction of development, operational – to improve processes, digital – to introduce new technologies, cultural – to adapt corporate values, and structural – to optimize the organizational hierarchy. Each type of transformation responds to specific needs and forms a holistic system for the successful development of the enterprise.

Therefore, effective transformation management is critical to the success of the enterprise. It allows us to respond to current challenges and pave the way for long-term development and sustainable success. Choosing the type of transformation and understanding the factors that stimulate change allows the company to use its resources as efficiently as possible and move forward confidently.

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